

DIGITAL ECONOMY: THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT AND MODERN OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPMENT IN THE COUNTRY

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Annotation: The article discusses the role of foreign investment in the development of the digital economy and their huge contribution to development. In today's globalization, digitalization is important to bring innovative technologies to enterprises.

Key words: digital economy, Big Data, artificial intelligence, robotics, foreign investment.

Introduction. In recent years, the importance of advanced technologies and innovations in the development of the economy is growing. The latest technologies can increase the efficiency of production and business processes. With the introduction of the latest technologies into all areas and spheres of human activity, traditional approaches and working methods have changed. The emergence and spread of information and communication technologies have affected the global economy to such an extent that a new phenomenon - the digital economy - has emerged. The digital economy is an economy based on digital technologies, but in many ways we understand that the digital economy conducts business operations in markets based on the Internet and the World Wide Web.

The results of analysis and discussion. The digital economy is a digital medium that allows you to significantly increase the efficiency of storage, sales and delivery of various industries, technologies, equipment, goods and services, based on the use of the results of the analysis of these processes and the processing of large amounts of data. data is an activity that is a key production factor.

Big Data technologies, artificial intelligence, neurotechnology, quantum technologies, Internet of Things, robotics and sensory, digital electronic platforms, cloud and mobile technologies, virtual and augmented reality technologies in the future of modern development , digital technologies such as crowdsourcing, blockchain technology, cryptocurrencies and ICO, 3D technology are playing a crucial role.

The growth rate of the digital economy in the world is almost 20 percent per year. In developed countries, the share of the digital economy in GDP has reached 7%. They are already reaping huge benefits from the introduction of the digital economy. In particular, the United States exports more than \$ 400 billion worth of

digital services annually. More than 5% of the country's GDP is directly related to the Internet and information and communication technologies. By 2025, U.S. industry is expected to generate an additional \$ 20 trillion from digitalization. Such economic efficiency is particularly high in consumer goods production (\$ 10.3 trillion), the automotive industry (\$ 3.8 trillion) and logistics (\$ 3.9 trillion). according to various studies, the share of the digital economy in the world economy ranges from 4.5 percent to 15.5 percent. The United States and the People's Republic of China account for nearly 40 percent of the value added created in the global information and communication technology sector and 75 percent of blockchain technology-related patents.

In the process of such rapid changes in the world community and the intensification of competition, it is true that without the widespread introduction of innovations and digital technologies, we will not be able to sustainably develop the economy and ensure its competitiveness in the near and long term. requires the strengthening of scientific and practical efforts.

According to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Although our country has risen by 8 places in the international index of information and communication technologies in 2019, it is still far behind. Most ministries, departments and enterprises are digitally Of course, we know very well that the formation of a digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and manpower. But no matter how difficult it is, if we do not start today, when will we start tomorrow ?! therefore, an active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities for the next five years.

Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, they reduce unnecessary costs. At the same time, the most serious flaw that worries and annoys me the most is that they are also an effective tool in overcoming the scourge of corruption. We all need to understand this deeply. Public and public administration, including the widespread introduction of digital technologies in the social sphere, can increase efficiency, in short, dramatically improve people's lives"²⁵.

Below are the top 10 digital tech articles on this site.

- Video technologies for working from home.
- GPS, What3Words and Location.
- 5G and Virtual Reality.
- Smart homes.
- Cloud and SaaS.
- Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Deep fake and AI.
- Bitcoin and blockchain.

²⁵ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis of January 24, 2020

Digital Technology Benefits

1. Social Connectivity
2. Communication Speeds
3. Versatile Working
4. Learning Opportunities
5. Automation
6. Information Storage
7. Editing
8. Accurate Duplication
9. GPS and Mapping
10. Transportation
11. Low Cost
12. Entertainment
13. News
14. Warfare
15. Banking and Finance
16. Smaller Sized Devices

We all know that a good education provides a great start in life. Digital technologies are not only changing what we need to teach our children (see case studies on Swinburne University and the esmart library Program), they are changing how we teach them. The pace of change in technology also means that we have to keep learning throughout our lives, keeping up-to-date with how technology can help us at home and at work. Students are increasingly using digital tools to access information and educational resources, many are completing qualifications largely online. As well as increasing access, particularly for people in regional and remote locations (see Mobile Black Spot Program case study), digital tools can provide all students with more tailored educational solutions that meet their particular needs.

Digital technologies foster ecological innovations that contribute to sustainable development by reducing environmental impacts and optimizing resource use. As these technologies evolve and converge with biotechnology and nanotechnology, they could generate exponential innovations that contribute to a sustainable future. Digitalization has both positive and negative impacts on the environment. On the one hand, it can dematerialize the economy by facilitating the supply of the digital goods and services that represent an increasingly large part of the economy and exports; an increase in the importance of digitally supplied services reduces movements and thence emissions. A more profound change in consumption is expected with the development of the product as a service (PaaS) model, which makes it possible to compare the desired outcome of using a product without purchasing it. Mobility as a service (MaaS) uses this model to combine transport services from public and private

providers through a unified gateway that creates and manages journeys. This reduces carbon emissions and optimizes the space occupied by vehicles, helping progress towards more sustainable cities.

Classification of digital platforms by function

Table 1

Operating platform	Uber, Gett, Yandex
Innovative platforms	Android, iOS, Microsoft Windows
Aggregate platform	Alibaba
Social platform	Facebook, Instagram,
Integrated platform	Apple: AppStore, iCloud
Investment platform	Kickstarter
Mobilized platform	CRM - tizimi
Learning platforms	You Tube, Coursera

A whole range of services that people use every day, including banking, shopping and entertainment are available online. Access to goods and services online is particularly important for Australians living in rural and remote areas. Data about the availability, cost and customer experience of services is helping us choose a restaurant for dinner, an energy provider or where to holiday. Government services are also increasingly available online with the aim to deliver seamless, painless and efficient services that protect people's privacy and security. Services including myGov and myTax are good examples of how the government is transforming the way Australians deal with government.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, it is important to cite 12 key signs that will transform the digital economy. These knowledge, in business and in the economy in general, the main focus is on the use of human capital-knowledge. Digitization - Now knowledge can be stored digitally. in the previous economy, data was analogous or physical, and information exchange took place only through direct human contact.

Virtualization - in the digital economy, it is possible to turn physical and material objects into virtual ones.

Dynamism - Traditional organizational structures allow for a more dynamic work environment.

Integration - a separate organization at the micro level has all the advantages of small companies due to new information and communication technologies.

Working without intermediaries - there is no need for intermediaries. Many organizations communicate directly with their customers through information and communication technologies, which facilitates the exchange of information between suppliers and customers.

Convergence is a leading sector of the economy, created as an convergence of communication and Internet technologies.

Innovation - The digital economy is based on innovation using information technology to develop new products and services

Changing producer-consumer relations - one of the important aspects in an industrialized society is mass production.

Efficiency - customers want more information and quality service.

Globalization - in a digital economy, when knowledge becomes the main resource, there is only one world economy, even if the organizational structures operate in their territories.

Disagreement - Every new development is followed by a change, as well as contradictions and slow adaptation to them.

In the digital economy, the gap between technologically literate professionals and those with no access to technology is widening and could lead to serious problems for society in the future. In the words of UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres, “The digital economy can pose new threats, including threats to cybersecurity, easing of illegal economic activity, and breaches of privacy. New decision-making governments , requires the concerted action of civil society, academic groups, the scientific community and the technology sector”.

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